

Contemporary bibliometric citation classics

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Introduction

The term “Classics” or, more specifically, “Citation Classics” is best known in the field of information science through Garfield’s introduction of *Citation Classics* (Garfield, 1977). After having discussed lists of the most-cited articles (Garfield, 1974), he came up with the idea of *Citation Classics*. Each week he selected an article that, as shown by its citations, had become highly cited (a classic) in its field. The authors of these classics were invited to provide a commentary, describing their contribution. In this way, these classics contributed to the human side of science.

In the present contribution, we focus on *Citation Classics* in bibliometrics and consider only recent citations and older publications (see further).

Data Collection and Methods

We used the Web of Science (WoS) as our database. Publications that articles or books published before 1991 and received the highest citations between 2012 and 2021 were regarded as Citation Classics. The field of bibliometrics was operationalized as all publications (in the WoS) published in the journals *Scientometrics*, *Journal of Informetrics*, *Quantitative Science Studies*, *Research Evaluation*, *Journal of the American Society* (since 2014: Association) *for Information Science and Technology*, and the *Journal of Data and Information Science*. We refer to these journals as “Bibliometric Sources”.

Result

Table 1 shows the list of the 20 most-cited publications of article-review type in recent times. We see that Garfield occurs three times in this list, Price, and Merton twice. These three scientists also wrote highly cited books (see Table 2). Garfield and Price are bibliometricians, but Merton, a sociologist, is not. Yet, he is the 1995 recipient of

the Derek de Solla Price award (together with Anthony van Raan).

Table 1. The top 20 Contemporary Bibliometrics Citation Classics

List of Citation Classics and Times Cited
Matthew Effect in Science (1968), <i>Science</i> , R. K. Merton - 233
Co-citation in the Scientific Literature (1973), <i>J. Am. Soc. Inform. Sci.</i> , H. Small - 210
Networks of Scientific Papers (1965), <i>Science</i> , D. J. de S. Price - 188
Citation Analysis as a Tool in Journal Evaluation (1972), <i>Science</i> , E. Garfield - 183
Citation Indexes for Science (1955), <i>Science</i> , E. Garfield - 154
Centrality in Social Networks Conceptual Clarification (1979), <i>Social Networks</i> , L. C. Freeman - 130
The Frequency Distribution of Scientific Productivity (1926), <i>J. Wash. Acad. Sci.</i> , A. J. Lotka - 124
A General Theory of Bibliometric and Other... (1976), <i>J. Am. Soc. Inform. Sci.</i> , D. J. de S. Price - 122
Bibliographic Coupling Between Scientific Papers (1963), <i>Am. Doc.</i> , M. M. Kessler - 121
Relative Indicators and Relational Charts for... (1986), <i>Scientometrics</i> , A. Schubert & T. Braun - 90
Is Citation Analysis a Legitimate Evaluation tool? (1979), <i>Scientometrics</i> , E. Garfield - 89
Author Cocitation (1981), <i>J. Am. Soc. Inform. Sci.</i> , H. D. White & B. C. Griffith - 83
Citation Influence for Journal Aggregates of... (1976), <i>Inf. Process. Manage.</i> , G. Pinski & F. Narin - 81
Absorptive Capacity (1990), <i>Admin. Sci. Quart.</i> , W. M. Cohen & D. A. Levinthal - 78
From Translations to...Co-word Analysis (1983), <i>Soc. Sci. Inform.</i> , M. Callon et al. - 73
Problems of Citation A... (1989), <i>J. Am. Soc. Inform. Sci.</i> , M. H. MacRoberts & B. R. Macroberts - 70
A Penny for Your Quotes: Patent Citations... (1990), <i>Rand J. Econ.</i> , M. Trajtenberg - 67
The Strength of Weak Ties (1973), <i>Am. J. Sociol.</i> , M. S.

Granovetter - 67
The Matthew Effect in Science, II: Cumulative advantage and ... (1988), <i>ISIS</i> , R. K. Merton - 64
Connectivity in a Citation Network (1989), <i>Social Networks</i> , N. P. Hummon & P. Doreian - 62
Assessing Basic Research (1983), <i>Res. Policy</i> , B. R. Martin & J. Irvine - 62

This list contains five articles published in the *American Journal of Information Science* (and its precursor *American Documentation*), four in *Science*, and two in the journals *Social Networks* and *Scientometrics*, which were only established in 1979. The majority of the items in this list deal with citation analysis. Several articles deal with network theory and the so-called bibliometric laws (but Bradford and Zipf are not present). Among our Citation Classics, 17 are written by Americans or colleagues who did the work in the USA (such as Price). We find ten Price awardees on the list, plus Price himself. One woman, Barbara MacRoberts, made the list, with Irina Marshakova's (1973) proposal of the notion of co-citation, published in the same year as Small's, only ending up much further.

How are these Citation Classics directly related? Do they build upon one another? Figure 1 shows the direct citation network among these articles. Garfield (1955), Garfield (1972), Price (1965), and Kessler (1963) are well-recognized, while the isolated nodes of Granovetter (1973), Cohen & Levinthal (1990), and Trajtenberg (1990) show that these authors are not information scientists, although their work is heavily used.

Figure 1. Direct citation network among Contemporary Bibliometrics Citation Classics

We also searched for citations to old books and found four that would figure among the top 20 in Table 1. As books are cited under many different forms, we show them separately and warn that the number of citations is probably a lower bound, see Table 2.

Table 2. Most-cited older books. Times cited refers to the period (2012-2021).

Books
<i>Little Science, Big Science</i> (M) (1963). D. J. de S., Price - 123
<i>On Theoretical Sociology: Five Essays, Old and New</i> (M) (1967). R. K. Merton - 100
<i>Citation Indexing Its Theory and Application in Science, Technology and Humanities</i> (M) (1979/1983). E. Garfield-100
<i>Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences</i> (M) (1988). J. Cohen - 74

Further Ideas and Preliminary Conclusions

In future research, we will study the complete list of cited items and compare the Classics shown here, referring to 2012-2021, with a similar list for 2001-2010. Constructing a co-citation network between these classics is another aim. We will further investigate the part of the Bibliometric Sources in the total of all citations over the corresponding period.

We think that every bibliometrician or investigator in the science of science should have read (most of) these classics and make sure that their students have. In this way, we think we made a small contribution to the education of future bibliometricians.

References

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